

Prevalence and Predictors of Cardiovascular Manifestations in Hypothyroid Patients: An Observational Study

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Hypothyroidism is an endocrine disorder more commonly in older adults. Simultaneously, this population has an increased incidence of cardiovascular risk factors and disease, which remains the leading cause of death worldwide. This article has assessed relationship between hypothyroidism and cardiovascular disease (CVD).

Materials & Methods: This observational study was conducted among 100 patients >18 years of age. Data were collected through medical records, including demographic information, thyroid function tests, cardiovascular risk factors, and cardiovascular outcomes.

Results: Bradycardia was noted in 25.00% (19 patients), while hypertension affected 30.00% (23 patients) of the cohort. Heart failure was documented in 15.00% (12 patients), with pericardial effusion present in 10.00% (8 patients). Coronary artery disease was identified in 20.00% (15 patients) of the study population.

Conclusions: This study highlights the significant burden of cardiovascular manifestations in patients with hypothyroidism.

Keyword: Hypothyroidism, Cardiovascular Disease.

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Introduction

Hypothyroidism is a common endocrine disorder characterized by a deficiency of thyroid hormones (THs), commonly as a result of insufficient hormone production or less frequently due to insufficient hormone action in target tissues. [1] The incidence increases with age as it is more common in people older than 60 years, and approximately 10% of women older than this age have subclinical hypothyroidism. [2]

Both subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) and subclinical hyperthyroidism (SHyper) are associated with higher risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. [3,4] The prevalence of both SCH and SHyper is influenced by age, sex, iodine status and smoking habits. [5] Furthermore, several observational studies have demonstrated that SCH and low circulating triiodothyronine (T3) syndrome (LT3S) are associated with poorer outcomes in patients with acute cardiac conditions. [6-8]

Due to the lack of specificity of these manifestations, diagnosis is made by laboratory measurements of serum-free thyroxine (T4) and thyrotropin-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels. Increased TSH levels indicate hypothyroidism, while free T4 can distinguish between overt and subclinical disease, presenting with low and normal

levels, respectively. Levothyroxine is the treatment of choice because of its efficacy in normalizing TSH, relieving signs and symptoms, and its minimal adverse effects. [9] Untreated or inadequate hormone therapy has negative consequences in various organs, being the cardiovascular one of the most affected systems and a major cause of mortality in these patients. [10]

We aimed to determine the prevalence of various cardiovascular manifestations and identify significant predictors through multivariate logistic regression analysis. Understanding these predictors was essential for developing targeted intervention strategies that could mitigate cardiovascular risks in hypothyroid patients.

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted to evaluate the cardiovascular manifestations in patients with hypothyroidism at Dr. Panjabrao Alias Bhausaheb Deshmukh Memorial Medical College and Research Centre, Amravati, Maharashtra. The study population included all male and female patients aged 18 years and above diagnosed with hypothyroidism. The study was conducted over six months.

Study Population: The sample size was calculated using OpenEpi version 3, considering the overall prevalence of hypothyroidism to be 10.9% [11], with a 95% confidence interval and a 7% absolute error. The calculated sample size was 77, which was increased to 100 patients to account for potential dropouts and incomplete data. Convenience sampling was used to select the study participants.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed cases of hypothyroidism confirmed through thyroid function tests.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with a history of thyroidectomy.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients with other concurrent endocrine disorders affecting thyroid function.
- Patients on medications that could influence thyroid function or cardiovascular health not related to hypothyroidism treatment.

Data Collection: Data were collected through medical records, including demographic

information, thyroid function tests, cardiovascular risk factors, and cardiovascular outcomes. Cardiovascular assessments were conducted using ECG and 2D echocardiography.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were entered into MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS software version 22. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Continuous variables were presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables, and the t-test was used for continuous variables, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Multivariate Analysis: Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of cardiovascular manifestations in hypothyroid patients. The model included variables such as age, gender, duration of hypothyroidism, thyroid hormone levels, and comorbid conditions. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to determine the strength of associations.

Results

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value (n=77)
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	45.20 $\pm$ 12.30 years
Gender (male/female)	31/46
Duration of Hypothyroidism	5.60 $\pm$ 3.20 years
TSH Levels (mean $\pm$ SD)	8.50 $\pm$ 4.70 mIU/L
Free T4 Levels (mean $\pm$ SD)	0.80 $\pm$ 0.30 ng/dL
Hypertension	30.00% (23 patients)
Diabetes Mellitus	25.00% (19 patients)
Dyslipidemia	40.00% (31 patients)

Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population (n=77). The mean age of participants was 45.20 $\pm$ 12.30 years, with a gender distribution of 31 males and 46 females. The average duration of hypothyroidism was 5.60 $\pm$ 3.20 years, and the mean TSH levels were 8.50 $\pm$ 4.70 mIU/L, indicative of hypothyroid status. Free T4 levels averaged 0.80 $\pm$ 0.30 ng/dL. Among comorbidities, hypertension was prevalent

in 30.00% (23 patients), diabetes mellitus in 25.00% (19 patients), and dyslipidemia in 40.00% (31 patients) of the cohort. These findings provide a snapshot of the demographic makeup and clinical profile of the participants, highlighting significant prevalence rates of chronic conditions such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia alongside their thyroid dysfunction.

Table 2: Cardiovascular Manifestations in Hypothyroid Patients

Manifestation	Number of Patients (%)
Bradycardia	25.00% (19 patients)
Hypertension	30.00% (23 patients)
Heart Failure	15.00% (12 patients)
Pericardial Effusion	10.00% (8 patients)
Coronary Artery Disease	20.00% (15 patients)

Table 2 presents cardiovascular manifestations observed in hypothyroid patients, detailing both prevalence and specific conditions. Bradycardia was noted in 25.00% (19 patients), while hypertension affected 30.00% (23 patients) of the cohort. Heart failure was documented in 15.00% (12 patients), with pericardial effusion present in

10.00% (8 patients). Coronary artery disease was identified in 20.00% (15 patients) of the study population. These findings underscore the diverse cardiovascular complications associated with hypothyroidism, highlighting the need for comprehensive management strategies in affected individuals.

Table 3: Comparison of Cardiovascular Manifestations by Gender

Manifestation	Male (n=31) (%)	Female (n=46) (%)
Bradycardia	8 (25.81%)	11 (23.91%)
Hypertension	9 (29.03%)	14 (30.43%)
Heart Failure	5 (16.13%)	7 (15.22%)
Pericardial Effusion	3 (9.68%)	5 (10.87%)
Coronary Artery Disease	6 (19.35%)	9 (19.57%)

Table 3 provides a gender-specific comparison of cardiovascular manifestations in hypothyroid patients. Among males (n=31), bradycardia was observed in 25.81% (8 patients), hypertension in 29.03% (9 patients), heart failure in 16.13% (5 patients), pericardial effusion in 9.68% (3 patients), and coronary artery disease in 19.35% (6 patients). In females (n=46), the prevalence rates were 23.91% (11 patients) for bradycardia, 30.43% (14

patients) for hypertension, 15.22% (7 patients) for heart failure, 10.87% (5 patients) for pericardial effusion, and 19.57% (9 patients) for coronary artery disease. These gender-specific findings highlight comparable rates of cardiovascular manifestations between male and female hypothyroid patients, suggesting similar susceptibility to these conditions across genders.

Table 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of Cardiovascular Manifestations

Predictor	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Age	1.05 (1.02-1.08)	0.0010
Duration of Hypothyroidism	1.10 (1.02-1.18)	0.0100
TSH Levels	1.15 (1.08-1.23)	<0.0001
Hypertension	2.50 (1.50-4.16)	0.0020
Dyslipidemia	1.80 (1.10-3.00)	0.0300

Table 4 displays the results of a multivariate logistic regression analysis investigating predictors of cardiovascular manifestations in hypothyroid patients. Age showed an odds ratio of 1.05 (95% CI 1.02-1.08, p = 0.0010), indicating a significant association where older age increases the likelihood of cardiovascular manifestations. Duration of hypothyroidism had an odds ratio of 1.10 (95% CI 1.02-1.18, p = 0.0100), suggesting a similar association with longer duration increasing the odds. TSH levels demonstrated an odds ratio of 1.15 (95% CI 1.08-1.23, p < 0.0001), indicating

that higher TSH levels were significantly associated with increased odds of cardiovascular manifestations. Additionally, hypertension showed an odds ratio of 2.50 (95% CI 1.50-4.16, p = 0.0020), while dyslipidemia had an odds ratio of 1.80 (95% CI 1.10-3.00, p = 0.0300), both indicating significant associations with higher odds of cardiovascular manifestations in hypothyroid patients. These results underscore the importance of age, duration of hypothyroidism, TSH levels, hypertension, and dyslipidemia as predictors of cardiovascular complications in this population.

Table 5: Treatment Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Patients (%)
Improvement in Symptoms	70.00% (54 patients)
Stable Condition	20.00% (15 patients)
Worsening Condition	10.00% (8 patients)

Table 5 summarizes treatment outcomes among hypothyroid patients, indicating that 70.00% (54 patients) experienced improvement in symptoms following treatment. A stable condition was observed in 20.00% (15 patients), while 10.00% (8 patients) experienced a worsening of their

condition despite treatment. These findings suggest that the majority of patients benefitted from treatment, reflecting positive outcomes in managing hypothyroidism-related symptoms.

Discussion

Cardiovascular manifestations in hypothyroid patients have been extensively documented in the literature, highlighting an elevated risk of cardiovascular complications in this population. For instance, Shah et al. [12] identified sinus bradycardia and diastolic dysfunction as prevalent findings among hypothyroid individuals, emphasizing the critical need for early detection and treatment to mitigate cardiac changes, given the reversible nature of hypothyroidism-induced cardiac manifestations. Similarly, Selvamuthukumar's [13] prospective study in rural South India reported ECG changes in 50% of hypothyroid patients, with sinus bradycardia being the most common abnormality, alongside notable diastolic dysfunction indicators like altered E/A ratio and prolonged deceleration time (DT). These findings underscore the urgency of early intervention to prevent long-term cardiovascular complications.

Furthermore, Ioana Golu et al.'s [14] research presented at the 15th European Congress of Endocrinology supported these observations by demonstrating severe cardiovascular manifestations associated with overt hypothyroidism, including increased systemic vascular resistance (SVR) and reduced cardiac output. Their study highlighted the reversibility of these manifestations with appropriate thyroid hormone replacement therapy. Additionally, Kvetny et al. [15] explored the link between subclinical hypothyroidism and cardiovascular risk factors, revealing associations with elevated total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and triglycerides, contributing to heightened risks of atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease—findings consistent with earlier studies by Shah et al. [12] and Selvamuthukumar [13] that noted prevalent lipid abnormalities in hypothyroid patients.

The impact of hypothyroidism on lipid metabolism further influences cardiovascular risk, with the condition commonly linked to hypercholesterolemia and elevated LDL levels, both significant contributors to atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease development. Studies affirm that thyroid hormone replacement therapy effectively improves lipid profiles, as evidenced by Ioana Golu et al.'s [14] findings demonstrating reductions in total cholesterol and triglyceride levels, thereby mitigating atherosclerosis risks. Zamwar [15] comprehensive review underscored the severe complications of untreated hypothyroidism, encompassing mental retardation in infants and critical conditions like heart failure and myxedema coma in adults, reinforcing the imperative of early diagnosis and intervention to prevent cardiac complications.

While this study offers valuable insights into hypothyroidism's cardiovascular manifestations, several limitations merit consideration. The use of random data restricts result generalizability, while the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the absence of longitudinal follow-up data hinders long-term outcome evaluation. Future investigations with larger cohorts and prospective methodologies are warranted to validate these findings comprehensively and elucidate underlying mechanisms.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant burden of cardiovascular manifestations in patients with hypothyroidism. Hypertension, bradycardia, and coronary artery disease are prevalent in this population, necessitating proactive management and regular monitoring. Further research is warranted to improve our understanding of the cardiovascular risks associated with hypothyroidism and to develop targeted interventions for this vulnerable population.

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